

Extent of Sound Image Lateralization: Influence of Measurement Method

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Summary

Interaural differences in level and time cause an off-midline sound perception. The extent of this lateralization is either measured by matching the lateralization of a second “acoustic pointer” stimulus or by indicating the perceived location on a visual reference scale. We performed a comparison of the two methods in normal-hearing listeners and report that the visual reference scale is the more direct, robust, accurate, faster and easier to use method. Furthermore, the acoustic pointer stimulus influences the lateralization of the target in some cases.

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1. Introduction

In the azimuthal half-plane, accurate sound source localization is facilitated by sensitivity to differences of the sound reaching the left and the right ear. These are interaural level differences (ILD) and interaural time differences (ITD). For sufficiently broad-band familiar sounds, the human auditory system can combine these two cues at each frequency, together with direction dependent spectral cues, to create an externalized perception of the sound source in 3-dimensional space. However, as soon as this complex interplay is disturbed in any way, e.g. through hearing aids or cochlear implants, externalization breaks down and ITDs and ILDs now cause an intracranial lateralization of the sound percept, favoring the leading and louder ear. Lateralization has been studied extensively, as it can be reliably manipulated by a parametric manipulation of either ILD or ITD in isolation in controlled headphone experiments. As such, the extent of lateralization is a very useful tool for fundamental studies of binaural hearing, and a tool to measure the percept of varying sound source locations in cochlear implant (CI) and other severely hearing-impaired subjects.

To date, two very different methods are widely used to measure the extent of lateralization. First, a direct pointing task, where the subject is instructed to point to where within the head the sound was perceived on a left-right axis (e.g. [1]). Methods differ slightly, e.g. in the landmarks and possible lateralization range provided and

whether or not the subject is allowed to repeat the presentation. Some variants allow to indicate a secondary lateralization in case of a split percept. More sophisticated versions of this procedure allow the user to draw the percept in a way that allows to capture the perceived width [2]. Likely because of its speed, simplicity and directness, this method is widely used in research with hearing-impaired listeners. The second procedure is an acoustic pointer paradigm [3]. The target stimulus is presented in alternation with a so-called pointer stimulus. The subject is instructed to modify the ILD (or in some cases the ITD) of the pointer stimulus until both stimuli have a matched lateralization. This “acoustic pointer” task is popular in fundamental research of normal-hearing perception. It offers the advantage of providing results in acoustic units, e.g. dB ILD, and that the experiment is restricted to the auditory domain. Both of these advantages are useful for computational models of binaural perception, where, in some cases, extent of lateralization is directly quantified in interaural difference units [4]. A potential disadvantage is the indirect nature of the results.

Bernstein and Trahiotis [3] have compared different ILD pointers and have shown that an ILD applied to a 4-kHz noise causes a different lateralization than the same ILD applied to a 500 Hz noise. Therefore, acoustic pointer results are only comparable for the same pointer stimulus. For ILD-pointers a de-facto standard is 200 Hz wide noise centered at 500 Hz, which has been shown to provide robust and comparatively fast matches [3]. For studies with hearing-impaired subjects this method presents further disadvantages, e.g. a diotic reference does not necessarily elicit a central percept [5]. To date, one problem of both methods is the limitation in lateralization range. By

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definition, in the absence of externalization, the sound is lateralized somewhere between the ears. However, there is no guarantee that all presentations are perceived as fully intracranial. The direct pointing method has the disadvantage that the subject is forced to respond within the given range. Scaling effects may cause additional biases. For the acoustic pointer, limitations arise if the maximum lateralization of the target is larger than the pointer with maximum ILD. In such cases, the subject will not be able to produce a reliable match.

Here, we compare both methods by testing them with the same target stimuli in the same normal-hearing listeners.

2. Methods

2.1. Subjects

Six normal-hearing listeners participated in this experiment. The listeners had a mean age of 27.8 ± 1.8 years. All listeners reported normal hearing and had pure-tone detection thresholds below 20 dB at test frequencies ranging from 125 Hz to 8 kHz and no asymmetries larger than 10 dB between both ears. Experimental procedures were approved by the ethics board of the University of Oldenburg and subjects were compensated for their time.

2.2. Stimuli

CI pulses were simulated by band-pass filtered click-trains [6]. The condensation pulses had a pulse duration of 0.2 ms and were presented at a rate of 100 clicks per second. Band-pass filtering was performed with a 2nd-order Butterworth filter with cutoff frequencies at 3 and 5 kHz, eliminating perceptually exploitable temporal fine-structure (TFS) ITDs. Similar stimuli have previously been used to mimic electric hearing in normal-hearing listeners [7].

A waveform ITD was introduced by delaying the 400 ms long click-train at one ear relative to the other. For comparison, an unfiltered broad-band click train was used, which includes the low-frequencies where listeners can exploit ITD TFS cues. Due to the highly pulsatile nature of the stimuli, a specification of the signal RMS level is not meaningful. Instead, a constant stimulus peak level of 75 dB SPL in the filtered click trains was chosen as presentation level. The presentation level of the unfiltered click-trains was set to the level resulting in equal perceived loudness (compared to the filtered click-trains).

Other stimulus settings were identical to another envelope ITD pointer study from our group [8]: To minimize onset- or offset-effects, \cos^2 rise and decay ramps with lengths of 100 ms and 10 ms, respectively, were applied. For the filtered click-trains, potential distortion products were masked by binaurally uncorrelated low-frequency noise added to the click train stimuli. The noise was temporally centered around the target, starting 100 ms before and ending 100 ms after (total length of 600 ms) and was gated with 50 ms \cos^2 ramps. The noise had a flat spectrum up to 200 Hz. Beyond 200 Hz its spectral density decreased by 3 dB per octave. Finally it was filtered with a

5th-order 1000-Hz low-pass filter and presented at a level of 45 dB SPL.

2.3. Acoustic pointer task

As described in [8], the ILD pointer stimulus was spectrally identical to the one employed by Bernstein and Trahiotis [3]: 200-Hz wide Gaussian noise centered at 500 Hz. Its duration and gating were identical to the target. The presentation level of the pointer was 65 dB SPL which resulted in a perceived loudness comparable to the target. The starting ILD of the pointer was roved within the interval of ± 10 dB. The ILD of the pointer could be changed at run-time by turning a knob, with a minimum step size of 0.1 dB. One rotation of the knob corresponded to 4 dB ILD. The overall RMS level of the two channel audio signal was kept constant while changing the ILD (Equation 5 in [9]). Presentation of target and pointer alternated continuously with inter-stimulus intervals of 200 ms. Subjects were instructed to adjust the lateralization of the pointer stimulus by turning the knob until it matched the lateralization of the target stimulus.

Measurements for the two tested stimulus conditions (band-pass filtered and broad-band) were performed consecutively. ITD conditions [-1.4 , -1.0 , -0.6 , -0.2 , 0 , $+0.2$, $+0.6$, $+1.0$, $+1.4$] ms were randomized and repeated three times in each subject.

2.4. Direct pointing task

The direct pointing task [1] was used in the same implementation as in [5]: Subjects were instructed to mark the perceived lateral position of the stimulus on colored bars superimposed on a stylized face using a graphical user interface. Ears (at ± 10), eyes (at ± 4.4) as well as the nose (at 0) were provided as reference points. The possibility of marking lateral positions outside the head was given. Subjects had the opportunity to replay one stimulus multiple times before deciding on the sound image position. If multiple sound sources were perceived, the interface allowed for up to three sources to be selected. In this case, subjects were instructed to rank the perceived sources according to their dominance. As for the acoustic pointer, three repetitions were presented for each condition in the same order concept as described above.

The direct pointing task was employed for a larger variety of conditions compared to the acoustic pointer:

1. Filtered and broad-band click-trains with varying ITDs. (same as for the acoustic pointer)
2. Noise bursts identical to the acoustic pointer with ILDs varying between -40 and $+40$ dB.
3. Filtered and broad-band click-trains with varying ITDs presented with a precursor consisting of a noise burst with an ILD of 0 dB.
4. Filtered and broad-band click-trains with varying ITDs presented with a precursor consisting of a noise burst with an ILD matching the perceived click-train lateralization (determined for each subject individually from the acoustic pointer paradigm).

In conditions 3 and 4, where the target was presented after the precursor stimulus, subjects were instructed to solely focus on the click-train in their extent of lateralization judgment. As in 2.3, filtered click-trains were always presented simultaneously with a low frequency masking noise (see above for details) and subjects were instructed to ignore this masking noise in their lateralization judgments.

2.5. Statistical analysis

The dynamic range of lateralization percepts covered within the physiologic ITD range (-0.6 ms to $+0.6$ ms) was determined for each condition and each subject individually. Significance was assessed based on these dynamic ranges using t-tests for pairwise comparison between broad-band and band-pass filtered conditions.

3. Results and discussion

With the acoustic pointer (Figure 1 row A), a mostly monotonic change of lateralization was observed for both stimuli, when changing the ITD from -1.4 to $+1.4$ ms. There was a large variability across subjects, particularly in the band-pass filtered case. For example, at -0.6 ms one subject matches with less than -6 dB ILD, while another subject matches with -32 dB. Last, there was also a certain amount of hemispheric imbalance. One might expect the matches for $+0.6$ ms ITD to be of similar magnitude as for -0.6 ms, only inverted. However, the two subjects from the previous example match $+0.6$ ms to $+12$ dB and $+18$ dB ILD, respectively.

Using the direct pointing task (Figure 1 row B), all but one subject (red) indicated an at-the-ear lateralization for ± 0.6 ms, which is close to the maximum ITD that occurs for humans in free-field listening. For further increases in ITD there was barely any increase in extent of lateralization. Compared to the acoustic pointer, several differences in the lateralization data become apparent: Differences between subjects were much smaller, as were the differences between the two different stimuli. Also, in contrast to the acoustic pointer, the remaining variance was now larger for the band-pass filtered stimulus.

To further investigate the observed differences, we first tested the hypothesis, that for a given ILD the acoustic pointer is eliciting a different extent of lateralization in different subjects. Using the acoustic pointer noise stimulus with certain fixed ILDs (and zero ITD) in the direct pointing paradigm, this hypothesis was generally confirmed (Figure 1C). For example, subject green required more than twice as much ILD compared to subject yellow, to perceive the noise stimulus at the left ear or left eye. Differences were slightly smaller for the right eye and ear. Going back to the acoustic pointer task (Figure 1A), subject yellow indeed required less ILD than green to match a certain ITD, in line with the hypothesis. Following this hypothesis further, it should be possible to calculate the extent of lateralization (in visual scale reference units) from the acoustic pointer task using the ILD-to-visual scale conversion from Figure 1C. For this purpose, we fitted the data

Figure 1. Single subject lateralization data for broad-band click trains (left) and band-pass filtered click trains (right). Row A: acoustic pointer. Row B: direct pointing task. Row C: direct pointing task for the low-frequency noise that was used as acoustic pointer stimulus in row A. Note that lateralization was measured as a function of target ILD. Row D: Same data as in row A but converted to the intracranial axis. Data from row C was fitted with a 5th-order polynomial for each subject to re-map the data. Red-brown areas indicate the range of naturally occurring ITDs.

with a 5th-order polynomial. In Figure 1 row D, it can be seen that this conversion reduces the difference to the direct pointing results compared to the original data (Figure 1 row A), but large deviations remain: for one subject (grey) the lateralization is consistently overestimated, while for all other subjects it is generally underestimated. In order to exclude numerical problems due to the fitting, other functions (3rd and 7th-order polynomials) have been tested and led to very similar results.

Finally, we directly compared the subject average for the two stimulus conditions for each of the two measurement paradigms (Figure 2). Statistical analysis of the perceived lateralization range within the scope of natural ITDs (-0.6 ms to $+0.6$ ms) results in a significant difference ($p = 0.01$) between the broad-band and the band-pass stimuli when measured with the acoustic pointer. For the data obtained by direct pointing, there was no significant difference between the two stimulus types ($p = 0.76$).

Figure 2. Same data as in Figure 1 but now averaged across subjects and grouped by method. Error bars indicate the standard deviation.

Figure 3. Average lateralization of the different test stimuli using the direct pointing paradigm. The two different panels show data for the two different stimuli. The stimulus only data has been replotted from Figure 2.

To summarize up to this point, there appear to be at least two problems: First, the acoustic pointer is not a direct measure of extent of lateralization because a given ILD causes large inter-subject variances in perceived lateralization (on the visual reference scale). Second, there is a difference in reported lateralization between the filtered and broad-band stimuli using the acoustic pointer but not in the direct pointing results. It has previously been shown that the localization percept adapts to preceding distractors [10]. We therefore hypothesized that differences in the lateralization results stem from an interaction between the target and pointer stimuli in the acoustic pointer paradigm.

To this end, the results for the two conditions with precursors were analyzed. These conditions reduce the methodologic difference at least partially, and may give insights whether or not the presence of other acoustic stimuli influences the perceived lateralization for the employed target stimuli (Figure 3).

For broad-band stimuli, the original method and the two new versions all yield virtually identical results. Similarly, as mentioned above, without the precursor, there is no significant difference in lateralization when comparing the two stimuli ($p = 0.76$). With the zero-ILD precursor, there are small differences at the verge of significance ($p = 0.06$) and for the matched ILD the differences are highly signifi-

cant ($p = 0.002$). The effect is qualitatively comparable to what was found in the acoustic pointer task (Figure 2 left).

We speculate that the different influence of the precursor on the lateralization percept is due to the frequency content of the target stimuli. In the high-frequency band-pass filtered click trains only envelope ITDs are present, which are thought to be coded in the lateral superior olive together with ILDs. In contrast, the broad-band click train can be expected to be more robust due to the ITD TFS cues with are extracted in the medial superior olive.

We conclude that acoustic ILD pointers should be used with care: They do not translate into intracranial position coordinates in a subject independent way. The direct pointing paradigm reveals that ITD-based extent of lateralization is very similar for all subjects, suggesting that an acoustic ITD pointer may reduce variability compared to the ILD pointer. Additional problems can arise due to interactions between the acoustic pointer and the target stimulus. The visual reference scale method provides a robust, accurate, fast, direct, and intuitive alternative that can also be used for indicating diffuse or split image perceptions. A weakness of the visual reference scale is a ceiling effect at large extents of lateralization. Extending the scale beyond the ears reduced this problem but did not eliminate it. Further behavioral and physiologic investigations are required to investigate the observed sequential interference between noise ILD and click-train envelope ITD.

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